

CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PATIENTS DURING STENTING WITH DIFFERENT TYPES OF STENT WITH BENIGN DYSPHAGIA

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Relevance: Dysphagia is a common condition that can seriously affect a patient's quality of life. It is a common symptom in the general population, with a prevalence of up to 20% and affecting up to 50% of people over 60 years of age. From an anatomical point of view, it can be due to oropharyngeal or esophageal etiology, while from a pathophysiological point of view, dysphagia can be caused by organic (benign or malignant) and functional diseases, causing mainly motor disorders.

Purpose of the study: to determine the features of the clinic of patients with stenting by various types of stent with benign dysphagia

Materials and methods: For the achievements set by the task of studying the features of benign dysphagia, we studied 60 patients with dysphagia syndrome caused by various benign pathologies of the esophagus. All patients were hospitalized at the Department of Surgery of the Esophagus and Stomach of the State Institution "Republican Specialized Center for Surgery named after N.N. acad. V. Vakhidov" for the period from 2000 to 2021

Conclusions: Thus, based on our research, we can conclude that among benign diseases of the esophagus, the most common post-burn cicatricial strictures (n=40) in 66.7% of the total number of patients (n=60), It should also be noted that due to the improvement of instrumental methods for the treatment of benign narrowing of the esophagus, post-burn cicatricial strictures, the number of patients requiring long-term intubation of the upper gastrointestinal tract has noticeably decreased.

When evaluating the results of stenting of 60 patients with PRSP and ESR, we, as in the case of a tumor lesion, evaluated both immediate and long-term results.

When evaluating the immediate results, it was found that, in the control group, out of 33 patients who used stents of their own design, all 100% had various complications. In the main group, out of 27 patients who used self-expanding

nitinol stents, complications were not observed in 17 patients, which amounted to 63%.

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